

Maxillofacial anomalies in children with chronic tonsillitis and immunity factors, hypoxia and endogenous intoxication for the development and formation of pathology.

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ABSTRACT

The study included 359 children with dental abnormality (MFA) among children aged 7-15 years; 138 children with chronic bronchitis (ChB) and (MFA); Chronic tanzanite (ChT) and (MFA) in 166 children; Of the 55 children, only MFA was examined, with an average age of 9 and 11 months. In patients with ChT and ChB based on the results of clinical orthodontic, biochemical and immunological studies; Reactivation of C-oxidative reactivity, the content of antistreptolysin-O and seromucoids in peripheral blood, Hetal Fetal hemoglobin - HbF, E - immunoglobulin in the blood, von Willebrand factors suggest that (MFA) is a leading factor.

Key words: MFA, ChB, ChT

Relevance work

In medicine, including dentistry, the question of the mutual correlation of various diseases and diseases of the oral cavity never fell out of sight of both domestic and foreign authors [16,19]. At the same time, information on the prevalence of dentition in children and adolescents with somatic pathology in the literature is not fully reflected. Many diseases that a child suffered in the first years of life, acting on various body systems, create a favorable background for the formation of MFA and deformities (MFI), these include rickets, chronic respiratory diseases [3,13,18], at the same time, some authors combine respiratory diseases and functional disorders in the dentofacial system (MFS) into a single pathogenetic chain [15,17,22].

Studies of domestic and foreign authors [2, 7,10, 15,17,23] the role of nasal breathing disorders in the formation of VHP during the change of teeth and a permanent bite was proved; or a violation of mental development in combination with general weakness, pallor, and reduced resistance to infection is a clinical characteristic of children with respiratory systems.

A number of studies have shown that brain nerve cells are more sensitive to oxygen deficiency and play a key role in angiogenesis with the involvement of endothelial factors in the pathological process [8, 25]. Under the influence of hypoxia, the release of fetal hemoglobin (HbF) is stimulated, which affects the progression of angiogenesis [1,6,9,20,24].

An assessment of ventilation and gas exchange in the lungs in patients with MFA was found that in children with incisive disocclusion of the dentition, the statistical and dynamic indicators of external respiration were reduced. Violation of nasal breathing is accompanied by endogenous intoxication syndrome, in the study of which there are no studies to model its main manifestations and to evaluate the diagnostic information content of individual indicators [14,21].

Thus, the multifactorial nature of the occurrence of MFA and new concepts of their development, including the presence of such factors as hyperplasia of the nasopharyngeal tonsil, dictate the need for further search and improvement of

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methods, diagnostics, prevention and treatment of diseases of the MFS in children combined with chronic tonsillitis (HT) and chronic bronchitis (HB)[4,5,11,12].

Purpose of this study

It turned out that the improvement of diagnostic methods for MFA in children with HT and HB based on the study of the characteristics of immunity and the biochemical composition of blood using clinico - orthodontic, biochemical, immunological socio-medical charts.

Objects and methods of research

The research was carried out: at the Department of "Dentistry, Pediatric Dentistry and Orthodontics" of TashIUV, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry and Orthodontics, BukhMI named after Abu. Ali Ibn Sin. Surveys of 359 children aged 7 to 15 years with MFA were living in the city of Bukhara, of which 166 patients were assessed as MFA with HT; 138 patients were determined with MFA with HB, the control groups followed 55 with MFA without somatic disease - HT and HB. Of the examined, 204 (56.8%) boys and 155 (43.2%) girls. The examination was carried out using the individual card "Orthodontic Patient Card" approved by the Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 7 dated 02.28.2018 on the basis of the standard WHO map with partial additions and changes to conduct a retrospective study of patients and their parents. The presence of MFA, confirmed with the help of an orthopantomogram, a teleroentgenogram, a photograph of occlusion of the dentition, given by biometric studies of control and diagnostic models of the jaws. The diagnoses of HT and HB are confirmed by the conclusions of the otorhinolaryngologist, allergist-pulmonologist and the patient's anamnestic card data questionnaire for this patient's parents, as well as the diagnosis of MFA was made according to the ICD-10 classification. The examination of children and adolescents was carried out in a dental chair using a mirror, a periodontal probe, an orthodontic ruler, a disposable glove, a pencil, and the aforementioned map was filled in for each column. Orthodontic measurements of bites by the method of Engel, using telerecography was evaluated by MFR,

cephalometric measurements by the method of Pont, Korhaus and Sinegey, with the orthopantomogram, the state of replacement of dairy and constants was assessed.

For biochemical studies, venous blood sampling in children was performed in the morning on an empty stomach. Blood cells were counted using a SysmexKX-21 hematology analyzer in capillary blood taken from EDTA. The acid-base condition of the blood was studied on a Micro-Astrup analyzer. The content of desquamated blood endotheliocytes was determined according to the method of Hladovec J (1978). To assess the degree of systemic activation of vascular endothelium, the plasma concentration of von Willebrand factor was determined and studied: lysozyme, lactoferrin, secretory immunoglobulin A in saliva (slg A), the amount of secretory immunoglobulin A, lactoferrin and lysozyme in saliva was also determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using HUMAN kits. To isolate and purify HbF, we used the methods of alkaline denaturation of 1.2 M NaOH, salting out with ammonium sulfate, gel filtration on a column with Sephadex G-25 (working buffer - 0.05 M phosphate buffer solution, pH 7.4) and ion-exchange chromatography on DEAE-Sephadex G-50 on 0.01 M Tris-chloride buffer pH 8.1. Quantitative determination of HbF was carried out by agar gel electrophoresis with sodium dodecyl sulfate. The content of C-reactive protein and the parameters of endogenous intoxication in the blood were studied on a Cobas-411 biochemical analyzer from ROSH (Switzerland). There were no gender differences in the control group.

Data analysis was performed using the STATISTICA v. 6.0 "for Windows XP. The relationship between the characters was studied using the Spearman (R) correlation analysis method. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

The results obtained and their discussion

The resulting data shows that mothers out of 359 examined children and adolescents, 1-trimester - 38.4%, 2-trimester - 37.0%, 3 - trimester - 15% and 4 - trimester 9.4% reported health problems during pregnancy, at the same time we found that children with HT and at the same time with

occlusion anomalies 64%, anomalies in the dentition 36%, mothers with a trimester, with HB and at the same time occlusion anomalies 22%, anomalies in the dentition - 26.3% , the same indicators at the 3rd trimester with chemotherapy 12%, 18.1% and with chronic hypertension 18% and 10.5%, respectively. And we also found out of the children under study - 51.9% of the cases were natural, 30.9% - mixed and 7.3% - with artificial types of feeding. Cht with occlusion anomalies - 60%, anomalies in the

dentition - 30.3%, by natural feeding, - 32% and - 63.3%, respectively, mixed and - 8%, - 6.06%, respectively, by artificial feeding of pytivalos. And with HB patients in patients with occlusion anomalies - 48%, anomalies in the dentition - 78.9% natural; - 22% and - 21%, respectively, with artificial or mixed types of feeding were growing. In the control group, these indicators amounted to 72.7%, 23.6%, and 3.6%, respectively.

Fig.1: Diseases of mothers during pregnancy by periods (by%)

With HT with occlusion anomalies combinations - among 7-10 years old - 41%, - 11-15 years old - 59%. Of these, regardless of age, in the middle - 19% - distal, 17% - reverse, 13% - medial bite, 16% - protrusion, 15% - shortening of the upper jaw and the rest 10% of me.

In CHB disease with occlusion anomalies combinations, among 7-10 years of age, 95%, 11-15 years of age was 5%. Of these, regardless of age, in the middle - 24% - distal, 6% - reverse, 17% - medial bite, 22% - protrusion, 12% - deep bite and the rest 10% of me.

In CHT, with a combination of a number of anomalies in the dentitions among the 7-10 years of age, 81.1%, and 11-15 years of age, were 18.8%. Of these, regardless of age, on average - 30.3% - dystopia, 41% - infraocclusion, 13.6% - diastema, 15.1% - supraocclusion; when combined with HB this figure is 18.4; - 67.7%; - 10.5%; - 10.5% respectively. Among 7-10 years of age - 94.7%; 11-15 years of age - in 5.4% of cases, anomalies in the dentition was noted.

According to the methods of Pon, Korhaus and Sinagina, the results of measuring the distance between teeth, jaw forms with a combination of CHT and CHB groups established a sufficient

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difference with the control groups and with morphological norms: By Pon; 7-10-year-old occlusion anomalies with a combination of CHT, the upper jaw between 4/4 teeth an average of 30.5 mm, 4 cutting teeth 24.5 mm, 6/6 teeth 49.5 mm, the lower jaw between 4/4 teeth an average of 35, 3 mm, 4 cutting teeth 27.5 mm, 6/6 teeth 45.0 mm; with a combination of CHB ohm of the upper jaw between 4/4 teeth on average 34.5 mm, 4 cutting teeth 27.5 mm, 6/6 teeth 46.2 mm, lower jaw between 4/4 teeth an average of 34.8 mm, 4 cutting teeth 27.0 mm,, 6/6 teeth 45.4 mm; a, in patients, the control group in the upper jaw - 29.1 mm; 24.0 mm; and 44 mm, respectively; on the lower jaw 32.6 mm; 26.0mm; 43.2 mm, respectively.

By the methods of Ponu; 7-10-year-old anomalies in the dentition with a combination of CHT, the upper jaw between 4/4 teeth an average of 37.5 mm, 4 cutting teeth 29.5 mm, 6/6 teeth 48.5 mm, the lower jaw between 4/4 teeth an average of 31, 1 mm, 4 cutting teeth 25.5 mm, 6/6 teeth 42.3 mm; with a combination of CHB ohm of the upper jaw between 4/4 teeth on average 34.4 mm, 4 cutting teeth 27.8 mm, 6/6 teeth 45.0 mm, lower jaw between 4/4 teeth an average of 35.5 mm, 4 cutting teeth 27.5 mm; 6/6 teeth 35.5 mm; in patients, the control group in the upper jaw was 34.4 mm; 27.0 mm; and 46.8 mm, respectively; on the lower jaw 32.6 mm; 25.0 mm; 43.2 mm, respectively.

According to the results, it is noted that, with CHT and CHB, the size of the distance between the teeth of the upper jaw is noticeably larger

compared to the control group, and in the lower jaw the main average size is the distance in the teeth less than the control. The same picture can be seen by the method of Korhaus.

By the methods of Snagina; 7-10 year old patients with occlusion anomalies with a combination of chemotherapy, apical base of the upper dentition 41.8 mm wide, 37.4 mm long; the apical base of the lower dentition is 33.0 mm wide and 36.1 mm long; 11-15 year old patients 33.0 mm, 33.1 mm; and 33.1 mm, 36.1 mm, respectively: - With a combination of CHB for 7-10 year old patients 33.3; 29.6; 30.0; 32.2 mm and 11-15 year old patients 38.4 mm; 33.5 mm; 34.1mm; 36.9 mm, respectively.

By the methods of Snagina; 7-10 year old patients with anomalies in the dentition with a combination of CHT, the apical base of the upper dentition is 36.2 mm wide and 31.9 mm long; the apical base of the lower dentition is 32.8 mm wide and 35.2 mm long; 11-15 year old patients 33.5 mm, 30.4 mm; and 30.8 mm, 33.1 mm, respectively: - With the combination of CHB for 7-10 year old patients 33.0; 32.9; 30.8; 32.6 mm and 11-15 year old patients 38.5 mm; 34.3 mm; 35.2mm; 36.5 mm respectively.

The determination of the size, position, correlation of teeth, dentitions and their development in dynamics in case of somatic disease with the combination of chemotherapy and chemotherapy according to the methods of Macnamara, TWEED, Downs is described in the following tables.

Table 1: The results of the cephalometric study among patients.

Factorlar	Norm	Patient		
		Chronic tonsillitis	Chronic bronchitis	Control group
Na-Perp to point A (mm)	0-1±0	-11,1	-21,6	-3,41
Mand.length (Go-Gn) (mm)бн	97-100±0	107,17	108	105,8
Max/length (Go-Point A) (mm)	80±0	82,38	83,74	80,8
Length (Go-Gn)- (Go-Point A) (mm)	Ўзгарувчан±0	24,7	23,06	24,9
Ant. fac. Ht (ANS-Menton) (mm)	57-58±0	64,64	63,77	65,3
Mand.toCranial Base (Pog-Na Perp) (mm)	Small(-8-6) ±0	-11,5	-8,64	-11,6

Upper I to Point A(mm)	4-6±0	-4,71	4,55	3,85
Lower I to Point A(mm)	1-3±0	2,56	1,11	16,3
Upper pharynx (mm)	15-20±0	22	14	12
Lower pharynx (mm)	11-14±0	18	12	11,4
FMA (deg)	22-28±0	29,07	25,75	29,24
FMIA (deg)	67±0	58,23	59,74	58,22
IMPA(deg)	88±0	57,1	93,26	92,5
Z angle (deg)	75±0	69,76	72,34	70,74
Facial angle (deg)	87,8±3,57	84,3	86,1	83,73
Angle of convexity (deg)	0±5,09	-15,41	6,13	6,63
A-B plane to facial plane (deg)	1,6±3,67	-3,7	-77,2	-6,13
Mandibular plane to F.H plane(deg)	21,9±3,24	29,0	27,1	29,24
Y axis angle (deg)	59,4±3,82	63,04	61,4	64,04
Occlusal plane to F.H plane (deg)	9,3 ±3,83	9,80	7,90	11,3
I to I (deg)	135,4±5,76	127,7	128,5	133,05
I to occlusal plane (deg)	14,5±3,48	22,0	23,07	20,4
I to Mandibular plane (deg)	2,7±1,80	2,71	-73,9	5,25

As can be seen from the presented research results (table No.), the blood hemoglobin indices in the examined children with MFA in combination with CHT and CHB were significantly reduced by 61% when compared with healthy children. In children with MFA, without pathology of CHT and CHB, the studied parameter

decreased compared with healthy children by 22%.

In the dynamics of fetal hemoglobin in the blood of the examined children, combined pathology, an increase in the blood level of children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB on average 1.6 times, indicating hypoxia.

Table 2: Biochemical blood parameters in children with MFA, in combination with ChT and ChB.

No	Indicators	Children with MFA combined with ChT and ChB n=304	Children with MFA, without pathology of the respiratory system n=55
	The hemoglobin content g / l	90,65±7,54*	116,48±9,13
	The content of fetal hemoglobin (HbF) (g / l)	3,78±0,19*	2,44±0,18
	pO2 arterial blood (mmHg)	65,32±5,43	70,45±6,38
	pO2 arteriovenous difference blood (mm. mercury. Art.)	23,14±1,58*	30,16±2,51
	pCO2 arterial blood(mmHg)	44,61±4,24	41,68±3,89
	The content of desquamated endothelial blood cells (x104 /l)	4,89±0,36*	3,23±0,24*
	Endothelin Content 1(fmol / l)	1,81±0,12*	1,06±0,11
	Von Willebrand factor (%)	118,06± 7,11*	95,34± 6,78*

Note: * - significance of differences P <0.05.

In establishing the relationship between changes in HbF and the concentration of such important markers of endothelial dysfunction as the

vasoconstrictor ET-1 and adhesive protein - von Willebrand factor, increased when comparing the results with the values of healthy children. A, a

comprehensive assessment of the levels of HbF, markers of endothelial dysfunction, with clinical data provides much more information about the development of tissue hypoxia and hypoxemia in children of MFA combined with ChT and ChB, and allows you to further evaluate the severity of the pathological process. In these children, in 44.2% of cases, a simultaneous increase in HbF concentration and a decrease in blood oxygen saturation of 65.32 ± 5.43 mm Hg were observed, versus 76.05 ± 6.11 mm Hg, indicating about moderate hypoxemia.

An indicator of the functional state of endotheliocytes is von Willebrand factor and endothelin-1. Willebrand factor is a complex multimeric adhesive glycoprotein synthesized by endothelial cells. The activity level of von Willebrand factor in blood plasma was also significantly higher than in healthy children. And the level of endothelin-1 in children with

combined ChT and ChB was significantly higher in comparison with healthy children. This fact is explained by the fact that with this pathology,

children have favorable conditions for the development of endothelial dysfunction, against the background of hypoxia, as well as impaired metabolic function of the endothelium, which lead to an increase in the content of biologically active substances.

An analysis of the obtained results of studies with MFA combined with ChT and ChB, showed a decrease in the level of class A antibodies in the blood serum by 38% relative to the parameters of the comparison group. As you know, when an antigen or endotoxins enters the body, plasma antibodies are initially synthesized by class-M antibodies. The obtained results of the studies presented in the table indicate an average decrease in this class of antibodies in the blood by 25% when compared with children with MFA without respiratory pathology system. The level of immunoglobulin - G is increased relative to the indices of the comparison group by an average of 16%, and similar dynamics was observed for immunoglobulin - E, where its concentration exceeded the indices of the comparison group by an average of 5 times.

Table 3: Indicators of systemic immunity in children with AF in the combination of ChT and ChB.

Class immunoglobulins ,	Children with RFA combined with ChT and ChB, n=304	Children with MFA, without pathology of the respiratory system
Ig A, мг/дл	$74,81 \pm 5,27^*$	$119,74 \pm 8,23$
Ig G, мг/дл	$1347,67 \pm 22,52$	$1158,17 \pm 19,56$
Ig E, мг/дл	$307,51 \pm 21,33^*$	$61,32 \pm 5,28$
Ig M, мг/дл	$80,24 \pm 7,04^*$	$107,56 \pm 8,21$

Thus, on the basis of the obtained research results, regarding the systemic immunity of the body of children with MFA, in combination with ChT and ChB, a scientifically substantiated new idea was formulated that allowed enriching the scientific concept of humoral immune system dysfunction and revealing new patterns of the studied combined pathology.

The lysozyme content in the saliva of children of the main group compared with the control is

reduced by 4.7 times in relation to the indicators of the comparison group. Significant is the decrease in the content of sIg A in the saliva of children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB by an average of 2.5 times.

The level of lactoferrin had a significantly reduced value in relation to the indicator of children with MFA, without pathology of the respiratory system, where it was equal to 876.51 ± 23.56 ng / ml, against 1628.93 ± 33.24 ng / ml in the study comparison group (table No. 2).

Table 4: Indices of local immunity (in saliva) in children with dentofacial anomalies in combination with adenoids.

Local rates immunity	Children with MFA combined with ChT and ChB n=304	Children with MFA, without pathology of the respiratory system
Lysozyme, mcg / l	0,49±0,03*	2,28±0,17
Lactoferrin, ng / ml	876,51±23,56*	1628,93±33,24
slg A, mg / l	98,38±8,16*	249,23±11,67

Note: * - significance of differences P <0.05

According to published data, the loss or absence of a portion of the GSTM1 gene leads to the absence of the corresponding enzyme involved in the detoxification of the xenobiotic and, therefore, the body's ability to metabolize the xenobiotic is reduced. In this situation, an increase in the level of immunoglobulin - E is observed under the influence of xenobiotics and allergens. The loss of the GSTM1 gene region and the high values of immunoglobulin - E, in our opinion, is one of the

predisposing factors for the aggravation of MFA in children with ChT and ChB. In studies in children with MFA combined with ChT and ChB,

the titer of antibodies to streptolysin of beta-hemolytic streptococcus was increased 2.5 times relative to the group of children without combined pathology, indicating the presence of concomitant somatic pathology and polyetiology of the disease (table No. 1).

And seromuroid in children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB hypertension is 2.9 times higher than a group of children without combined pathology. The main place for the synthesis of serum seromuroid is hepatocytes. Moreover, the main role in starting the synthesis of this protein belongs to IL-1 and IL-6. We know that C-reactive protein with great consistency is determined in the acute phase of diseases accompanied by inflammation syndrome and necrobiosis. Using this test, one can judge the severity of the pathological process, the depth and severity of tissue destruction.

Table 5: Parameters of endogenous intoxication syndrome in the peripheral blood of children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB.

Indicators and unit	Children with MFA with ChT and ChB n=304	Children with MFA, without pathology respiratory system n=55
Seromuroid, Food	0,35±0,02*	0,12±0,01
C-reactive protein, mg / l	9,78±1,04*	3,23±0,12
Antistreptolysin-O, IU / ml	298,47±11,31	119,25±8,52
Bilirubin, μmol / L	13,24±0,93*	8,45±0,71
Urea, mmol / L	4,32±0,28	3,72±0,24

Creatinine, $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$	78,12 $\pm$ 5,31*	56,38 $\pm$ 3,47
Sialic acids, mmol / l	1,61 $\pm$ 0,12*	2,43 $\pm$ 0,17

Note: * -reliability of differences $P < 0.05$

As can be seen from the presented research results, in children with MFA, in combination with ChT and ChB, an increase in the level of a reactive bun in the blood plasma was 3 times higher than in the comparison group. It is characteristic that during the same period in the liver cells of the examined children the formation of other plasma proteins and, above all, albumin, decreases. The analysis of the obtained results regarding the state of the liver and kidneys indicates the degree of adaptation of the organism of children associated with the property of inhibiting proteolytic enzymes (proteases) released during the destruction of the cell and capable of causing secondary tissue damage, as well as inhibiting autoimmune aggression. The quantitative changes we have established for endogenous intoxication syndrome in children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB help to identify leading indicators: C-reactive protein, antistreptolysin-O and seromuroid in the peripheral blood, which provide a complete

diagnosis of this combined form of the disease in children.

Findings:

It was noted in children with MFA with combinations of ChT and ChB, all points of measurement of bone elements and teeth by orthodontic parameters are noticeably deviating from the control group and from the morphological norm. The dependence of the partial oxygen parameters in the blood and, to a greater extent, HbF on the blood content of the vasoconstrictor endothelin-1, von Willebrand factor, was observed, which indicates the pathogenetic value of the leading markers of endothelial dysfunction in the development of tissue hypoxia in children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB. The immunodiagnostic parameters of blood and saliva in children with MFA in combination with ChT and

ChB should be recommended as markers for diagnosing the concentration of peripheral blood of immunoglobulin E. Quantitative changes in endogenous intoxication syndrome in children with MFA in combination with ChT and ChB help to identify leading indicators: C-reactive protein, antistreptolysin-O and seromuroid in the peripheral blood, which provide the diagnosis of this combined form of the disease.

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